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Mixed Ligand Complex Formation by Adenine and Hypoxanthine

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THERE is growing interest in the metal complexes of purines, pyrimidines and their nucleotides in view of their dominant role in many biochemical systems^{1,2}. In the present work, interactions of 6-aminopurine (adenine) and 6-hydroxypurine (hypoxanthine) with trivalent Y, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er and Tm have been studied by pH-titration methods in aqueous solution at 20° ($\mu=0.1 M KNO_3$). The ligands in their mixtures with tripositive rare earth ions form a number of mixed complexes. The stability constants of these complexes have been evaluated and the results discussed.

Experimental

Standard solutions of 0.1273 N NaOH, 1.0 M KNO_3 and 0.0234 N HNO_3 were prepared using analytical grade reagents. Y^{III} , Tb^{III} , Dy^{III} , Ho^{III} , Er^{III} and Tm^{III} carbonates were precipitated from their chloride salts (Johnson Matthey). Excess of carbonate was treated with standard nitric acid solution and filtered. Metal content was determined gravimetrically after precipitation as oxalate and subsequent ignition to oxide. Aqueous solutions of 6-aminopurine (adenine, HA) and 6-hydroxypurine (hypoxanthine, H_2B) (each, Loba) were prepared.

Procedure: The following aqueous mixtures were prepared and titrated^{3,4} against NaOH solution (0.1273 N) using a Systronic 335 pH meter: (i) 0.00234 N HNO_3 ; (ii) $5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$ ligand + (i); (iii) $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ metal nitrate + (ii); (iv) $2.5 \times 10^{-4} M$ metal nitrate + (ii); (v) $1.66 \times 10^{-4} M$ metal nitrate + (ii); (vi) metal nitrate + adenine + hypoxanthine + (i) ($C_M^0 = C_A^0 = B_B^0 = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, where the symbols are total initial metal, adenine, hypoxanthine concentration, respectively); (vii) metal nitrate + adenine + hypoxanthine + (i) ($C_M^0 = 1/2 C_A^0 = C_B^0 = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$); (viii) metal nitrate + adenine + hypoxanthine + (i) ($C_M^0 = C_A^0 = 1/2 C_B^0 = 5.0 \times 10^{-4} M$).

Experiments were carried out, keeping the initial volume of each mixture 50 cm³ at an ionic strength of 0.1 M KNO_3 at 20°. The pH-metric titrations were continued to a pH of ~11.0.

From the experimental data, pH vs volume of alkali plots were utilised to calculate moles of alkali used per mole of ligand (a) at various pH. The a

values were further plotted against pH, and the titration curves thus obtained were analysed as described earlier^{3,4}, for obtaining informations on metal-ligand interactions.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand dissociation constant: Proton-ligand dissociation constants of adenine and hypoxanthine evaluated with the help of the titration curves (Fig. 1) by the previously described methods³ are given in Table 1. From a comparison of the values with those of other purine derivatives reported by earlier workers^{2,5} it is concluded that protons from amino (protonated) and hydroxy groups, respectively in adenine and hypoxanthine, are liberated at lower pH values (curve for adenine at lower pH not given) while those from imino groups of both the ligands dissociate at higher pH values.

Fig. 1. pH vs (a) curves for Dy^{3+} -adenine-hypoxanthine complex systems: (●) HA, (○) H_2B , (◐) Dy^{3+} -HA, (◑) Dy^{3+} -2HA, (⊖) Dy^{3+} -3HA, (*) Dy^{3+} - H_2B , (▲) Dy^{3+} -2 H_2B , (⊗) Dy^{3+} -3 H_2B , (⋯) Dy^{3+} -HA- H_2B , (Δ) Dy^{3+} -2HA- H_2B , (γ) Dy^{3+} -HA-2 H_2B .

Binary complexes: 1:1, 1:2, 1:3 metal (Y^{III} , Tb^{III} , Dy^{III} , Ho^{III} , Er^{III} , Tm^{III})-adenine mixtures, respectively remain turbid above pH ~7.66, 8.00, 7.65, 7.60, 7.56, 7.50; 8.10, 8.08, 7.82, 8.28, 8.32, 8.28; 8.55, 8.25, 8.50, 9.20, 8.68, 8.62; thus, beyond these pH values calculations could not be

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TABLE 1—EQUILIBRIUM CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND MIXED LIGAND COMPLEXES OF ADENINE AND HYPOXANTHINE

Temp = 20°, $\mu = 0.1 M$ KNO₃

Reaction	Log K						
	H ⁺	Y ³⁺	Tb ³⁺	Dy ³⁺	Ho ³⁺	Er ³⁺	Tm ³⁺
H ₂ A ⁺ ⇌ HA + H ⁺	-4.25 ± 0.04	—	—	—	—	—	—
HA ⇌ A ⁻ + H ⁺	-9.95 ± 0.06	—	—	—	—	—	—
H ₂ B ⇌ HB ⁻ + H ⁺	-8.52 ± 0.08	—	—	—	—	—	—
HB ⁻ ⇌ B ²⁻ + H ⁺	-10.29 ± 0.05	—	—	—	—	—	—
M ³⁺ + A ⁻ ⇌ MA ²⁺	—	5.66 ± 0.15	5.73 ± 0.29	5.86 ± 0.26	6.12 ± 0.35	6.13 ± 0.46	6.15 ± 0.37
MA ²⁺ + A ⁻ ⇌ MA ₂ ⁺	—	5.55 ± 0.13	5.54 ± 0.18	5.79 ± 0.04	5.92 ± 0.15	5.93 ± 0.21	5.98 ± 0.25
MA ₂ ⁺ + A ⁻ ⇌ MA ₃	—	5.33 ± 0.08	5.24 ± 0.28	5.58 ± 0.19	5.59 ± 0.20	5.63 ± 0.23	5.71 ± 0.20
M ³⁺ + B ²⁻ ⇌ MB ⁺	—	6.45 ± 0.20	6.89 ± 0.30	7.48 ± 0.19	7.78 ± 0.18	7.26 ± 0.27	7.29 ± 0.24
MB ⁺ + B ²⁻ ⇌ MB ₂ ⁺	—	6.00 ± 0.15	5.84 ± 0.32	6.44 ± 0.76	5.33 ± 0.62	4.82 ± 0.25	4.86 ± 0.24
MB ₂ ⁺ + B ²⁻ ⇌ MB ₃ ⁺	—	5.88 ± 0.42	4.26 ± 0.43	4.42 ± 0.16	3.92 ± 0.28	3.90 ± 0.04	4.03 ± 0.02
M ³⁺ + A ⁻ + B ²⁻ ⇌ MAB	—	14.01 ± 0.16	13.77 ± 0.09	14.19 ± 0.50	14.05 ± 0.42	14.25 ± 0.10	14.32 ± 0.41
MA ²⁺ + B ²⁻ ⇌ MAB	—	—	8.35	8.04	8.33	7.93	8.12
MB ⁺ + A ⁻ ⇌ MBA	—	—	7.56	6.88	6.71	6.27	6.99
M ³⁺ + 2A ⁻ + B ²⁻ ⇌ MA ₂ B ⁻	—	22.71 ± 0.51	21.55 ± 0.46	21.48 ± 0.38	20.78 ± 0.59	22.21 ± 0.55	22.43 ± 0.37
M ³⁺ + 2B ²⁻ + A ⁻ ⇌ MB ₂ A ²⁻	—	21.98 ± 0.24	20.71 ± 0.35	20.39 ± 0.36	21.49 ± 0.33	21.67 ± 0.28	22.16 ± 0.56
MA ₂ ⁺ + B ²⁻ ⇌ MA ₂ B ⁻	—	—	11.50	10.28	9.83	8.74	10.15
MB ₂ ⁺ + A ⁻ ⇌ MB ₂ A ²⁻	—	—	9.53	7.98	6.97	8.38	9.59
MA ₂ ⁺ + 2B ²⁻ ⇌ MAB ₂ ²⁻	—	—	16.32	14.98	15.03	15.37	15.54
MB ⁺ + 2A ⁻ ⇌ MBA ₂ ⁻	—	—	11.20	14.66	14.00	13.00	14.95

made. Analysis of pH vs (a) curves of the hypoxanthine complex systems also could not be made at higher pH values due to the appearance of turbidity from pH ~7.88, 8.15, 7.76, 8.10, 8.75, 8.74; 8.90, 9.35, 9.00, 8.98, 9.45, 9.55; 9.02, 10.16, 9.82, 10.48, 10.48, 10.44, respectively in the cases of the corresponding metal-hypoxanthine mixtures. Equilibrium constants evaluated by the previously described methods are given in Table 1. Simultaneous formation of complexes in solution is indicated by the shape of the titration curves (Fig. 1, for Dy^{III} systems, others not given), their analysis, and subsequently from the evaluated equilibrium constants. Stability constant of hypoxanthine complexes is greater than that of adenine probably due to stronger donor properties of oxygen atom than other atoms⁶. K_1 values for adenine complexes increase with decreasing ionic size of metal ions while those for hypoxanthine do not follow any regular decreasing or increasing order. Stepwise equilibrium constants generally follow the order .

$$K_1 > K_2 > K_3.$$

Mixed-ligand complexes: Turbidity appears from pH ~7.94, 7.73, 7.78, 7.85, 7.85 and 7.79, respectively in 1:1:1 mixtures of metal (Y^{III}, Tb^{III}, Dy^{III}, Ho^{III}, Er^{III} and Tm^{III}) with adenine-hypoxanthine. However, the titration curves (Fig. 1, for Dy^{III} system) indicate the formation of ternary complex species in solution below the pH of precipitation. Substituting the proton-ligand dissociation constant of the ligands and the equilibrium constants of their binary complexes into mass and charge valence relations, the concentrations of ligands were calculated by Newton-Raphson method as described earlier^{3,4}. Further, concentration of other species were obtained and the equilibrium constants of the mixed ligand species MAB were evaluated (Table 1). The data indicate that mixed ligand complex forma-

tion is highly favourable in all the systems. Formation constant for the addition of second ligand to 1:1 metal-first ligand species are from 0.15 to 1.9 logarithm unit higher than that for addition of the second ligand to the hydrated metal ion. Thus, the present findings are in agreement with those of the mixed complexes of Cu^{II} ion reported by L'ttevreux and Martell⁷.

The formation of 1:1:2 metal-adenine-hypoxanthine and metal-hypoxanthine-adenine complex is also evident from the corresponding titration curves. However analysis of the data could not be made at higher pH values due to the appearance of turbidity from pH ~9.45, 9.74, 9.75, 9.66, 9.65 and 9.60; 9.20, 9.14, 9.02, 8.98, 8.92 and 8.92, respectively in 1:1:2 mixtures of tripositive rare earth ions Y, Tb, Dy, Ho, Er and Tm with adenine-hypoxanthine and hypoxanthine-adenine. Addition of second ligand in the formation of the mixed ligand species can be compared with the observations of Perrin and Sharma⁸ on the serine, ethylenediamine, histamine complexes with Ni^{II} ion. Mixed ligand complex formation with a high value of equilibrium constant is probably favoured by electrostatic interaction between the aminohydrogen of adenine and the oxygen of the hypoxanthine.

References

1. R. L. KARPEL, K. KUSTIN and M. A. WOLFF, *J Phys Chem.*, 1971, **75**, 799; K. H. SCHELLER, F. HOFSTELTER, R. PAUL, MITCHELL, B. PRIJS and H. SIGEL, *J Am Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **103**, 447; M. M. TAQUI KHAN and A. E. MARTELL, *J Am. Chem Soc.*, 1966, **88**, 668; J. GALRA, R. BACCARIA, G. FERRONI and J. P. BELOICH, *Electrochim Acta*, 1978, **23**, 647; C. R. KRISHNAMOORTHY, R. VAN ELDIK and G. M. HARRIS, *J. Coord Chem*, 1980, **10**, 195; D. W. DARNALL and E. R. BIRNBAUM, *J. Biol Chem.*, 1970, **245**, 6484; *Biochemistry*, 1973, **12**, 3489; *Met. Ions Biol. Systems*, 1976, **6**, 275;

- H. SIGEL, *Met. Ions. Biol. Systems*, 1973, **2**, 65 ; 1976, **5**, 148, 250 ; 1979, **9**, 66, 1320 ; SABHAPATI, Ph.D. Thesis, Rohilkhand University, 1987.
2. M. M. TAQUI KHAN and C. R. KRISHNAMOORTHY, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1971, **33**, 1417 ; R. NAYAN and A. K. DEY, *Z. Naturforsch., Teil B*, 1972, **27**, 688.
 3. R. NAYAN and A. K. DEY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 892.
 4. R. NAYAN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1981, **43**, 383.
 5. N. REINERT and R. WEISS, *Hoppe Seyler's Z. Physiol. Chem.*, 1969, **350**, 1310 ; A. ALBERT and E. P. SERJENT, *Biochem. J.*, 1960, **76**, 621.
 6. E. R. BIRNBAUM and T. MOELLER, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **91**, 7274 ; L. T. CHARPENTIER and T. MOELLER, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 3575 ; J. H. FORSBERG and T. MOELLER, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1969, **8**, 883, 889 ; R. C. GRAHDEY and T. MOELLER, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 333.
 7. G. A. L'ETEVREUX and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1966, **28**, 481.
 8. D. D. PERRIN and V. S. SHARMA, *J. Chem. Soc. A*, 1968, 446.